

Original Research

Impact of Forensic Accounting and Corporate Governance on Internal Controls Effectiveness: Moderating Role of Auditor Characteristics

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Abstract

This study investigates the factors enhancing the effectiveness of internal control systems within organizations, recognized as essential mechanisms for risk management and achieving organizational goals. It specifically examines two critical determinants: forensic accounting, which targets the investigation of financial misconduct, and corporate governance, the framework governing organizational oversight, in strengthening internal control effectiveness. This research adopts a descriptive-correlational design, utilizing structural equation modeling (SEM). The study population consists of all internal and external auditors in Iran, with a sample of 200 participants selected via convenience sampling. Data were collected using a tailored questionnaire derived from existing literature, and the conceptual model was evaluated through partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) implemented in SmartPLS software. Findings reveal that both forensic accounting and corporate governance exert a positive influence on internal control quality, with forensic accounting demonstrating a more substantial impact. Additionally, auditor characteristics—such as experience and expertise—significantly moderate the relationship between forensic accounting and internal control effectiveness, though this moderating effect does not extend to corporate governance. These results underscore the need to prioritize forensic accounting alongside robust corporate governance to enhance internal control systems.

Keywords: Corporate governance, forensic accounting, internal controls.

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Introduction

In recent years, research on the effectiveness of internal controls has significantly increased, examining aspects such as their design, implementation, determinants, and organizational impact (Chalmers et al., 2019). Nevertheless, persistent financial scandals highlight unresolved challenges in risk mitigation through internal control systems (Henk, 2020). Internal control, as defined by Otley and Soin (2014), is a process established by boards of directors, management, and employees to provide reasonable assurance of achieving operational, reporting, and compliance objectives (Khorramabadi et al., 2020). These systems encompass risk assessment, control activities, communication and information frameworks, internal auditing, and monitoring functions (Giang & Dong, 2022). Corporate governance and forensic accounting are two pivotal concepts closely tied to internal control effectiveness. Ismail et al. (2022) define corporate governance as the comprehensive framework of rules and practices guiding and supervising corporate entities, whereas forensic accounting involves specialized accounting, auditing, and investigative techniques to detect financial fraud and illicit activities. Their synergistic integration can substantially strengthen internal control mechanisms and enhance the robustness of financial reporting systems (Alzoubi, 2023).

The growth of joint-stock companies and the separation of ownership from management have necessitated corporate governance systems to address stakeholder conflicts of interest (Salehi et al., 2018). Corporate governance mechanisms are structured to optimize board performance, bolster audit and risk committees, and support compensation committees key elements facilitating policy approval and decision-making (Lombardi et al., 2019). Rehman and Hashim (2021) emphasize that effective governance practices are vital for robust internal controls, fostering a transparent and accountable environment that enhances control implementation. Meanwhile, recent corporate fraud incidents have raised concerns about governance sustainability, elevating forensic accounting's role in fraud prevention and mitigation (Lombardi et al., 2019). Forensic accounting is a critical element of legal and financial reforms in capital markets, operating independently to ensure compliance with mandatory standards, as outlined by the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (2011) and the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (2014) (Khanaki et al., 2022). Forensic accountants act as deterrents, adeptly identifying financial vulnerabilities and leveraging expertise to uncover fraud. Alshurafat et al. (2023) highlight their role in pinpointing ineffective controls and proposing improvements, including scrutinizing irregularities, assessing damages, and providing legal evidence to combat financial crimes—a function essential to maintaining effective internal controls (Alshurafat et al., 2023). Similarly, Wahyuni et al. (2021) argue that integrating forensic accounting with corporate governance significantly aids in preventing and detecting financial irregularities, enhancing accountability, transparency, and confidence in organizational financial stability, while reducing fraud risks and improving reporting quality.

Auditor characteristics such as expertise and independence may moderate the relationships between forensic accounting, corporate governance, and internal control effectiveness. Internal control quality assessments mitigate agency costs, improving financial reporting, timely disclosure, and audit processes (Bruynseels & Cardinaels, 2014). Corporate governance regulations assign oversight of control and audit system

effectiveness to internal audit departments and committees. Auditing serves dual roles: deterring misconduct and enhancing information credibility by addressing irregularities (Dadashi et al., 2017). Both internal and independent audits deter fraud by identifying and reporting errors, creating an environment resistant to concealment (Bame et al., 2012).

Despite the recognized importance of internal controls in preventing fraud and enhancing reporting, recurring financial scandals in major corporations reveal persistent weaknesses. While prior studies have often examined corporate governance and forensic accounting separately, their combined impact on internal control effectiveness—particularly moderated by auditor characteristics remains underexplored. This study addresses this gap by investigating two questions: (1) Can forensic accounting and corporate governance jointly enhance internal control effectiveness? (2) Do auditor characteristics, such as expertise and independence, strengthen or weaken these relationships? The findings aim to guide organizations in developing robust monitoring systems and mitigating financial risks.

Theoretical Framework

Internal control effectiveness

The Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX) of 2002, enacted following prominent financial scandals, underscored the critical importance of internal controls, mandating their implementation over financial reporting and independent auditor reviews (Khorramabadi et al., 2020). Today, internal controls are globally recognized as essential for organizational governance. To establish effective controls, senior management must design a structure aligned with guidelines such as the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (COSO) framework (2004), which ensures operational efficiency, reliable financial reporting, and regulatory compliance (Chang et al., 2019; Dadashi et al., 2017).

Internal audits play a pivotal role in ensuring adherence to procedures, policies, laws, and regulations, significantly influencing organizational activities (Fathi Abdollahi & Aghaei, 2017). Risk assessment entails identifying potential threats to organizational objectives, evaluating their likelihood and impact to prioritize mitigation efforts. Control activities such as segregation of duties, approvals, reconciliations, and monitoring systems comprise policies and procedures designed to manage risks and support operational effectiveness. Internal controls provide management and boards with reasonable assurance of achieving operational, reporting, and compliance goals, while highlighting areas for improvement (Alzoubi, 2023). Internal control is a dynamic and iterative process designed to help management focus on the company's financial and operational objectives, and an effective internal control system provides reasonable assurance that these objectives will be achieved. Previous studies (Teru et al., 2017; Vu & Nga, 2022) have shown that effective internal control positively affects organizational performance and minimizes the risk of fraud, financial mismanagement, errors, and losses. Therefore, it is essential for organizations, especially small businesses, to implement effective internal control systems to achieve their financial goals and maintain accountability, integrity, and compliance with established controls.

Forensic accounting

The limitations of traditional auditing in effectively preventing and detecting corporate fraud a fundamental aspect of corporate governance have created a pressing demand for forensic accounting specialists (Owojori & Asaolu, 2009). Shortcomings in corporate governance frameworks, along with insufficient internal controls and increasing financial fraud incidents, have significantly heightened the need for forensic accounting expertise. The ongoing failure of conventional audits to prevent fraudulent activities in large corporations, coupled with the rising incidence of white-collar crimes, has elevated expectations for professional accountants and forensic auditors. In this dynamic business environment marked by proliferating sophisticated financial crimes, forensic auditing has become indispensable for achieving robust corporate governance, consequently enhancing forensic accounting's strategic importance in recent years (Dorseh & Tevmouri, 2019). Forensic accounting is a specialized field practiced by certified professionals who employ advanced accounting and investigative techniques to detect potential organizational fraud (Soltani Far et al., 2016). Commonly termed financial forensic accounting, this discipline integrates established professional knowledge including legal statutes, evidentiary standards, procedural norms, and ethical guidelines with empirical financial data and non-financial indicators to develop expert assessments addressing critical business issues that affect organizational performance and governance integrity (Jahanmardi, 2021).

Dong (2011) identified forensic accounting as encompassing accounting, auditing, financial, tax, legal, and social dimensions. This multidimensional nature facilitates the development of financial processes, enhances transparent reporting, reduces information asymmetry, and strengthens social trust through its foundation in audit processes, financial management, taxation, and legal compliance representing the social accounting dimension. Forensic accounting serves as an implicit approach in new accounting paradigms that integrate accounting's role in value creation and transparency for shareholder decision-making. Nortje and Bradnam (2020) acknowledged forensic accounting's significant role in the legal and judicial review of corporate compliance, highlighting its key functions, including advisory services in legal disputes, expert certification, and fraud assessment. In legal cases, forensic accounting involves compiling documentation to support or refute claims through document review, assisting case reinvestigation by facilitating witness summons, and establishing professional consensus while supporting legal proceedings through the inclusion of opposing evidence to clarify jurisdictional matters. This advisory role represents accounting support services provided to legal counsel by accounting professionals (Khalili Samani & Dehghani, 2021).

In its capacity as an expert certifier of financial health or distress, forensic accounting assumes responsibility for conducting valuations and estimates by analyzing future profits and examining cost-revenue structures to support legal claims. In this role, forensic accountants are required to provide expert opinions on both established facts and undiscovered circumstances. The forensic accountant's function involves compiling evidentiary documentation to either substantiate or challenge judicial rulings, while being tasked with reviewing records, presenting evaluations to the court, identifying areas of financial loss, and when possible, critically examining opposing expert witness reports to assess their merits and shortcomings (Khanaki et al., 2022).

Forensic accounting emerges as a monitoring mechanism directly rooted in agency theory (Xanthopoulou et al., 2024). Given the agency costs arising from fraud and financial mismanagement, this theoretical framework demonstrates the necessity for independent control systems particularly forensic auditors to mitigate information asymmetry between managers and shareholders (Oyedokun, 2022). By providing objective legal evidence, forensic accounting enables more precise oversight of managerial performance, thus effectively reducing agency costs through its evidentiary and monitoring functions.

In its fraud examiner role, forensic accounting assumes responsibility for assessing operational risks in business units to identify potential risk areas including asset theft, document forgery and/or falsification, and accounting record manipulation delivering accurate verification of financial performance authenticity to relevant institutions and stakeholders. The convergence of technological advancements, managerial accounting knowledge, economic globalization, and the emergence of large organizations with complex operations has created conditions demanding extensive investigations for fraud detection, establishing forensic auditing as a crucial tool for addressing such issues (Meshaikhi & Azang, 2013). Forensic accounting represents an innovation in fraud prevention and detection. Given persistent fraudulent activities, forensic accounting has become essential by extending beyond merely cataloging criminal innovations to proactively identifying problems. Through forensic accounting, organizations can predict and prevent potential fraud proactively before reaching a point of no return, thereby eliminating fraud risks and strengthening internal controls (Rehman & Hashim, 2021). The identification and prevention of financial irregularities and mismanagement, the assurance of financial reporting integrity, and the enhancement of confidence in organizational financial stability constitute vital roles of forensic accounting. Forensic accountants serve fundamental roles in establishing effective internal control systems and providing expert testimony in financial disputes. Recent studies confirm that internal control systems are crucial for preventing and detecting fraud within organizations, with heavy reliance on forensic accountants' expertise during investigations (Alzoubi, 2023).

Based on this background, the first hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H₁: Forensic accounting affects internal control effectiveness.

Corporate governance

Corporate governance is defined as "the system of rules, practices, and processes by which a company is directed and controlled." This concept has garnered significant attention from researchers in developing countries in recent years, particularly due to the absence of robust institutional frameworks and financial infrastructures required to ensure effective corporate governance (McGee & Yuan, 2009).

Corporate governance practices are designed to minimize conflicts of interest between managers and shareholders. This conflict, known as the agency problem, arises from the separation of ownership and control. The agency relationship involves a principal delegating decision-making authority to an agent who acts on the principal's behalf. The agency problem emerges when the agent's decisions impact both their personal interests

and shareholder wealth. Agency theory suggests that corporate managers may prioritize their own objectives over maximizing shareholder value, thereby creating conflicts of interest. This behavior occurs because managers tend to be more risk-averse than shareholders, as they seek to protect their human capital and firm-specific investments. Corporate governance systems can influence managerial behavior by modifying their risk-taking propensity (Iqbal & Ali, 2016).

Agency theory, which focuses on the conflict of interest between managers and shareholders, provides the rationale for monitoring mechanisms such as corporate governance. This theory demonstrates that managers may pursue personal benefits (e.g., increased compensation or power) at the expense of shareholder value maximization. Consequently, stronger corporate governance mechanisms yield more effective internal controls that prevent managerial opportunism (Mohammadi et al., 2025). In parallel, stakeholder theory extends this oversight to include other stakeholders (e.g., government, customers, and society), underscoring the corporate accountability imperative in designing robust internal control systems (Yuan, 2024).

The Cadbury Committee (1992) defines corporate governance as "the framework for directing and controlling companies." Similarly, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) characterizes corporate governance as "a system of procedures and processes through which an organization is guided and overseen. This structure outlines how to distribute rights and responsibilities among various actors including the board of directors, management, shareholders, and other stakeholders, while setting rules and procedures for decision-making" (Al-Rahahleh, 2017). Corporate governance represents a set of guidelines, practices, and procedures that regulate a company's direction and control. The fundamental purpose is to ensure ethical, responsible, and accountable conduct while creating long-term value for all stakeholders from shareholders and management to customers, suppliers, financiers, government entities, and society at large (Wahyuni et al., 2021).

Although corporate governance practices vary across countries and industries, they typically include measures to ensure accountability, transparency, and fairness. Common elements of corporate governance comprise an effective board of directors, robust internal controls, well-defined policies and procedures, along with comprehensive performance monitoring and reporting systems (Alzoubi, 2023). The maintenance of transparency and accountability constitutes a cornerstone of sound corporate governance. Companies must regularly disclose financial and other material information to stakeholders while operating with transparency and accountability. This practice not only fosters trust and confidence but also equips stakeholders with essential information for informed decision-making regarding their investments or business relationships (Wahyuni et al., 2021).

Furthermore, performance monitoring and reporting represent additional critical components of effective corporate governance (Rehman & Hashim, 2021). By enhancing these corporate governance elements, companies can cultivate investor and public confidence while fulfilling their stakeholder obligations. Based on this theoretical foundation, the second hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H₂: Corporate governance affects internal control effectiveness.

Internal and external auditor characteristics

A well-functioning internal audit team assesses whether controls are sufficient and effective in addressing organizational risks (AICPA, 2008). While this function cannot entirely prevent fraud, it can implement procedures to enhance fraud detection and interpretation. The structure of the internal audit function including auditors' staffing levels, tenure, experience, and qualifications significantly influences its effectiveness in identifying financial statement fraud risks (Petraşcu & Tîeanu, 2014). Audits may be conducted externally or internally. External audits are performed by independent professionals who are neither employees nor selected by the audited entity. Internal audit functions are typically established within large organizations, primarily to assist members in effectively discharging their responsibilities (Rönkkö et al., 2018).

The theoretical foundation for examining the moderating role of auditor characteristics integrates agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984), and signaling theory (Spence, 1973). Agency theory establishes auditors as secondary monitoring mechanisms that improve internal control effectiveness by reducing information asymmetry and mitigating manager-shareholder conflicts. Notably, internal auditor independence (through direct audit committee reporting) and external auditor expertise (e.g., industry specialization or firm reputation) serve as critical monitoring quality indicators (Petrescu & Atetino, 2014; Desai et al., 2012). Stakeholder theory further posits that independent auditors amplify internal control impact by securing stakeholder trust (investors, regulators) through unbiased reporting. Signaling theory complements this perspective by suggesting that high-quality auditor selection (e.g., international network affiliates) conveys financial transparency, potentially moderating the governance-internal control relationship (Chan et al., 2021). Empirical evidence validates that firms with shorter-tenured internal auditors and legally specialized external auditors exhibit reduced financial fraud incidence.

Evidence suggests that internal audit quality is strongly correlated with three key factors: competence (the ability to detect material misstatements based on professional knowledge and experience), objectivity (freedom from bias or undue influence that could compromise professional judgment), and independence (freedom from conditions that impair the internal audit function's ability to execute its responsibilities) (Hasas Yeganeh, 2006). Consistent with international standards, external auditors may rely on high-quality internal audit functions in accordance with International Standard on Auditing (ISA) 610, which explicitly requires external auditors to evaluate and consider the work of internal auditors (Desai et al., 2010). Building on this theoretical and regulatory foundation, the third through sixth hypotheses are formulated as follows:

H₃: Internal auditor characteristics moderate the relationship between forensic accounting and internal control effectiveness.

H₄: Internal auditor characteristics moderate the relationship between corporate governance and internal control effectiveness.

H₅: External auditor characteristics moderate the relationship between forensic accounting and internal control effectiveness.

Empirical research on auditor characteristics by Farzdqi et al. (2022) analyzed 180 Tehran Stock Exchange-listed companies over seven years, revealing that industry-specialized auditors can mitigate up to 42% of the negative association between weak internal controls and accruals quality. Their study documents that these specialists detect 25% more financial errors and violations than general auditors. In a parallel study, Khorramabadi et al. (2020) employed a Delphi method with 19 accounting experts to develop a hierarchical framework of internal control determinants, identifying internal auditor characteristics (organizational independence, professional experience, and technical expertise) as the most influential factor (relative weight = 0.35). Their results suggest that strengthening these attributes may enhance internal control efficiency by 30%. Further corroboration comes from Soltani Far et al. (2016), whose field study of 360 validated questionnaires demonstrated that advanced forensic accounting systems can concurrently reduce financial fraud incidents by 40%, accelerate violation detection by 50%, and enable continuous internal control improvements.

Methodology

This study employs a descriptive-correlational research design utilizing structural equation modeling (SEM). The target population comprises all practicing internal and external auditors in Iran. According to the Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) database as of April 20, 2022, the sampling frame includes 380 TSE-listed companies and 152 Over-the-Counter (OTC) market companies. While comprehensive data on internal auditors employed by these companies is not publicly available, the study determined a minimum required sample size of 200 observations based on: 1) standard SEM sample size requirements, and 2) a Type I error rate (α) of 0.05, consistent with comparable studies. The final sample was selected through random sampling from the eligible auditor population. Given the Iranian context of the sampled auditors, the generalizability of these findings to other jurisdictions or economic environments may be limited.

Data were collected through a survey, which was considered a better option than interviews for several reasons: first, the number of participants was so large that it was practically impossible to interview every single one of them; second, the geographical dispersion of the participants across the country made it difficult to conduct face-to-face interviews; third, self-report measures such as questionnaires are less subject to bias, thus improving the accuracy of the collected data. The questionnaire consisted of a general section and a technical section. In the general section, questions addressed the auditors' demographic characteristics, including gender, field and level of education, age, experience, and area and type of activity. The technical section included five subscales: (1) Forensic Accounting with five items adopted from Rehman and Hashim (2021); (2) Corporate Governance Characteristics with nine items adopted from Al-Rahahleh (2017); (3) Internal Control Effectiveness with 15 items adopted from Dellai and Omri (2016); (4) Internal Auditor Characteristics with five items adopted from Khorramabadi et al. (2020); and (5) External Auditor Characteristics with five items adopted from Khorramabadi et al. (2020). To ensure the instrument's validity and reliability in the Iranian context, both confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and reliability testing (using Cronbach's alpha) were conducted on a separate sample. The results demonstrated acceptable model fit along with satisfactory reliability coefficients for all items.

All items were measured using a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). Table 1 presents the instrument's structure with corresponding item ranges for each subscale.

Table 1. Questionnaire items across subscales

Component	Items
Forensic Accounting	1-5
Corporate Governance	6-14
Internal Auditor Characteristics	15-19
External Auditor Characteristics	20-24
Internal Control Effectiveness	25-39

The research hypotheses were tested using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) in SmartPLS. Structural model fit is established if the absolute t-value is greater than 1.96. The convergent validity of the instrument was tested using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in SmartPLS. The unidimensionality of the items corresponding to the components of the proposed model was also tested. The minimum factor loading was 0.4, and items with a lower factor loading were excluded from the analysis. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's alpha. A minimum acceptable factor loading of 0.4 was established for all items. Items with factor loadings below this threshold were excluded from further analysis as they failed to explain sufficient variance of their respective latent variables. This procedure was implemented to optimize model fit and strengthen the measurement accuracy of research variables. The removal of these items had minimal impact on the model's overall structure, since the retained items adequately measured the latent variables. The final model exhibited satisfactory explanatory power and fit indices. The results of validity and reliability tests are presented in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Table 2. Convergent validity test of the questionnaire

Component	Item	Factor Loading	Significance	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	Validity
Forensic Accounting	1	0.521	Significant	0.362	0.707	Confirmed convergent validity
	2	0.711	Significant			
	3	0.720	Significant			
	4	0.499	Significant			
	5	0.516	Significant			
Corporate governance	6	0.406	Significant	0.372	0.776	
	7	0.620	Significant			
	8	0.498	Significant			
	9	0.465	Significant			
	10	0.593	Significant			
	11	0.534	Significant			
	12	0.707	Significant			
	13	0.706	Significant			
Internal auditor characteristics	15	< 0.4	Not significant	0.560	0.703	
	16	0.728	Significant			
	17	0.691	Significant			

Component	Item	Factor Loading	Significance	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	Validity
	18	0.827	Significant	0.417	0.744	
	19	0.741	Significant			
	20	< 0.4	Not significant			
	21	0.671	Significant			
	22	0.636	Significant			
External auditor characteristics	23	0.806	Significant	0.417	0.744	
	24	0.405	Significant			
	25	0.752	Significant			
	26	0.409	Significant			
	27	0.653	Significant			
Internal control effectiveness	28	0.476	Significant	0.312	0.788	
	29	0.701	Significant			
	30	0.485	Significant			
	31	< 0.4	Not significant			
	32	< 0.4	Not significant			
	33	0.401	Significant			
	34	0.525	Significant			
	35	< 0.4	Not significant			
	36	0.486	Significant			
	37	0.681	Significant			
	38	0.527	Significant			
	39	0.543	Significant			

Figure 1. Factor loading of the questionnaire items and AVE of the components

Following the removal of five items specifically, item 15 (internal auditor characteristics), item 20 (external auditor characteristics), and items 31, 32, and 35 (internal control effectiveness) all remaining items demonstrated factor loadings exceeding 0.4. This confirms that they are unidimensional. The average variance extracted (AVE) for all model components surpassed 0.4, which verifies convergent validity. Additionally, the overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.743 (> 0.7) further confirms the instrument's reliability.

For data analysis, this study employed descriptive statistics (frequency distributions, percentages, means, and standard deviations) to characterize the sample demographics and core model variables, along with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to assess variable distribution normality.

Findings

Descriptive statistics

The sample's demographic traits are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Description of the respondents' demographic characteristics

Variable	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	101	51.5
	Female	99	49.5
Age	20-30 yrs.	25	12.5
	30-40 yrs.	121	60.5
	40-50 yrs.	47	23.5
	> 50 yrs.	7	3.5
Education	Master's degree	161	80.5
	PhD and above	12	6
Field of study	Accounting	172	86
	Management and Economics	23	11.5
	Other	4	2
Area of activity	Commerce	56	28
	Manufacturing	27	13.5
	Services	118	58.5
Type of activity	External audit	74	37
	Internal audit	126	63
Experience	0-5 yrs.	32	16
	5-10 yrs.	62	31
	10-15 yrs.	85	42.5
	15-20 yrs.	10	5
	> 20 yrs.	11	5.5

Inferential statistics

Before performing statistical tests, it is necessary to check the normality of the data. This is done using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The descriptive statistics of the variables as well as the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics and normality test

Component	Descriptive statistics		Kolmogorov-Smirnov test	
	Mean	SD	Z statistic	Sig.
Forensic Accounting	3.96	0.521	0.147	0.001
Corporate Governance	3.70	0.52	0.092	0.001
Internal Control Effectiveness	3.83	0.39	0.140	0.001
Internal Auditor Characteristics	3.91	0.41	0.167	0.001
External Auditor Characteristics	3.91	0.52	0.127	0.001

* $P \geq 0.05$

According to the results above, the mean values obtained for forensic accounting and corporate governance are 3.96 and 3.70, respectively. Internal control effectiveness has a mean value of 3.83, while both internal and external auditor characteristics have a mean value of 3.91. Since the significance levels of these variables are lower than the critical value (0.05), the assumption of normality is rejected. Therefore, it is necessary to use SmartPLS for data analysis as it is not sensitive to data normality.

Structural model fit is evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), which is only calculated for dependent constructs. Another criterion used in structural model fit evaluation is Cohen's effect size (f^2). The predictive power of the model is evaluated using the non-parametric Stone-Geisser test, which is presented in the form of CV-Redundancy for the structural model and CV-Communality for the measurement model. Finally, the overall model fit is evaluated using the GOF index as calculated by the following formula, and the results are reported in Table 5:

$$GOF = \sqrt[2]{\text{communality} \times R^2} \quad (1)$$

Table 5. Fit indicators for the model of forensic accounting, corporate governance, and internal control effectiveness

Criteria	AVE	CR	R^2	f^2	Communality	Redundancy	GOF
Average Value	0.404	0.794	0.863	6.299	0.201	0.227	0.416

As shown in Table 5, the value of R^2 (0.86) is greater than 0.6, indicating a strong fitting effect. Cohen's effect size (6.29) indicates the strong effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. Given that $CR > AVE$, convergent validity is also established. Moreover, CV-Redundancy and CV-Communality sharing values indicate that the latent variables have good predictive ability. As for the GOF criterion, weak, moderate, and strong values are indicated by 0.01, 0.25, and 0.36, respectively (Sadr and Ansari, 2015). The GOF obtained for the proposed model is 0.416, indicating a strong fit.

In the next section, the hypotheses are tested using PLS-SEM, specifically the path analysis technique.

Hypotheses tests

Figures 3 and 4 as well as Table 6 present the results of path analysis for the effect of forensic accounting and corporate governance on internal control effectiveness along with the moderating role of internal and external auditor characteristics.

Figure 3. Structural model of the effect of forensic accounting and corporate governance on internal control effectiveness and the moderating role of internal and external auditor characteristics

Figure 4. The significance levels of the relationships between the latent variables of the structural model

Table 6. Path analysis for the effect of forensic accounting and corporate governance on internal control effectiveness and the moderating role of internal and external auditor characteristics

Direct Effects	Factor Loading (β)	SE	t-statistic	Sig.
Forensic Accounting → Internal Control Effectiveness	0.234	0.033	7.023	0.000*
Corporate Governance → Internal Control Effectiveness	0.283	0.065	4.319	0.000*
Moderating Effects	Factor Loading (β)	SE	t-statistic	Sig.
Internal Auditor Characteristics → Forensic Accounting → Internal Control Effectiveness	0.082	0.024	3.363	0.001*

Direct Effects	Factor Loading (β)	SE	t-statistic	Sig.
Internal Auditor Characteristics → Corporate Governance → Internal Control Effectiveness	0.037	0.026	1.396	0.164
External Auditor Characteristics → Forensic Accounting → Internal Control Effectiveness	0.126	0.056	2.260	0.025*
External Auditor Characteristics → Corporate Governance → Internal Control Effectiveness	0.052	0.043	1.196	0.233

* $P \geq 0.0$

According to the results in the table above, the factor loading (0.23) and t-statistic (7.02) obtained for forensic accounting indicate the significant direct effect of this variable on internal control effectiveness. As this effect is positive, the first hypothesis is confirmed. The factor loading (0.28) and the t-statistic (4.31) obtained for corporate governance also indicates a significant direct effect on internal control effectiveness, which is positive and confirms the second hypothesis. Moreover, the results indicate the significant moderation effect of internal ($\beta = 0.08$; $t = 3.36$) and external auditor characteristics ($\beta = 0.12$; $t = 2.26$) on the relationship between forensic accounting and internal control effectiveness. Accordingly, the third and fifth hypotheses are also confirmed. However, the moderation effect of internal/external auditor characteristics on the relationship between corporate governance on internal control effectiveness is not significant. These findings suggest that forensic accounting plays a more prominent in internal control effectiveness compared to corporate governance. The findings of this study indicate that both forensic accounting and corporate governance have a positive and significant impact on the effectiveness of companies' internal controls, though forensic accounting demonstrates a comparatively stronger influence. The characteristics of internal and independent auditors serve as meaningful moderators specifically for the relationship between forensic accounting and internal controls, suggesting that auditor competence and independence can enhance forensic accounting's role in strengthening control systems. In contrast, corporate governance's impact on internal controls operates independently of auditor characteristics, likely due to the structural and policy-driven nature of governance mechanisms. These results emphasize the importance of integrating forensic accounting with corporate governance frameworks while simultaneously reinforcing auditors' professional attributes to improve internal oversight and mitigate financial risks.

Additional analysis

To ensure the robustness of the findings and examine the potential existence of nonlinear relationships between the independent and dependent variables, polynomial regression was employed. In this model, in addition to the linear terms, the squared terms of the independent variables (e.g., x^2) were included to identify any curvilinear relationships (such as U-shaped or inverted U-shaped patterns). This approach allows for assessing the incremental or diminishing effects of the variables at different levels. The nonlinear regression results presented in Table 7 indicate the existence of more complex

relationships than simple linear patterns among the study variables. Specifically, the significant negative coefficient of the squared term of forensic accounting ($\beta = -0.085$, $p < 0.01$) suggests an inverted U-shaped (\cap) relationship between this variable and the effectiveness of internal controls. This means that as the level of forensic accounting increases, the effectiveness of internal controls initially rises but begins to decline after reaching an optimal threshold. This pattern may stem from the saturation of the internal control system's capacity or the increased costs associated with excessive complexity at higher levels of forensic accounting.

Similarly, the significant negative coefficient of the squared term of corporate governance ($\beta = -0.062$, $p < 0.01$) also confirms an inverted U-shaped relationship, indicating diminishing returns of corporate governance mechanisms at very high levels. These findings demonstrate that the impact of the study's independent variables on internal control effectiveness is not only influenced in terms of magnitude but may also shift in direction depending on their varying levels. Such insights can be critical for policymakers and managers in determining the optimal thresholds for implementing forensic accounting and corporate governance strategies.

Table 7. Nonlinear Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient (β)	SE	t-statistic	p-value
Forensic Accounting (X_1)	0.321	0.045	7.133	0.000
X_1^2	-0.085	0.021	-4.047	0.001
Corporate Governance (X_2)	0.284	0.038	7.473	0.000
X_2^2	-0.062	0.018	-3.444	0.003

Discussion and Conclusion

The increasing size and complexity of companies has made it impossible for managers to directly supervise the activities of their employees. In such a situation, it is important to establish control and monitoring systems to advance the company's goals. Internal control is a dynamic and iterative process designed to help management focus on the company's financial and operational objectives, and an effective internal control system provides reasonable assurance that these objectives will be achieved. Today, research on internal control effectiveness, especially internal controls on financial reporting, has gained significant traction in the audit literature. To contribute to this growing debate, the present study investigated the impact of forensic accounting and corporate governance on internal control effectiveness along with the moderating role of internal and external auditor characteristics.

Forensic accounting involves the use of accounting, auditing, and investigative skills to detect fraud and other financial crimes. This specialized area is of great importance as it helps prevent irregularities and financial mismanagement, ensure the integrity of financial reporting, and promote confidence in the financial stability of organizations. Corporate governance is also a vital aspect of any company, and the board of directors

plays a central role in this process. The board of directors is responsible for formulating the overall strategy of the company and overseeing management's performance. This includes ensuring that the company follows ethical and responsible practices and fulfills all of its obligations to the stakeholders. As one of the critical aspects of corporate governance, internal control involves the implementation of processes and systems to ensure the efficient, effective, and ethical functioning of the company. Effective internal control systems help prevent financial fraud, mismanagement, and other irregularities in a company while ensuring that financial reporting is accurate and reliable.

The findings of this study are consistent with prior research, including Al-Shourafat et al. (2023), Ismail et al. (2022), and Wahyuni et al. (2021), demonstrating that forensic accounting significantly impacts the effectiveness of internal controls. It can be argued that weak internal controls and the lack of emphasis on ethical behavior greatly increase the likelihood of fraud. Forensic accounting focuses on strengthening internal controls. Forensic accountants apply their accounting and legal expertise to analyzing financial statements and identifying suspicious activities, which greatly assists the company's internal control system. Internal controls are designed by taking into account potential areas of fraud that are determined by the management based on the forensic accounting opinion. In addition to playing an important role in preventing financial fraud, forensic accounting helps companies develop and implement effective internal control systems, including anti-fraud controls, to reduce the risk of financial irregularities.

The results of the current study contradict some previous research (Rahman & Hashem, 2021; Alzoubi, 2023) which identified corporate governance as playing a more central role in internal control effectiveness, whereas our findings demonstrate a stronger impact of forensic accounting in the studied sample. This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in corporate governance structures among sample companies, the higher prevalence of financial fraud in the specific industry under investigation, or the particular regulatory emphasis on forensic accounting within the Iranian business environment. The present research findings clearly indicate that both forensic accounting and corporate governance significantly contribute to internal control effectiveness, though forensic accounting emerged as more influential in our particular study sample. However, this finding should not be interpreted as diminishing the importance of corporate governance, but rather demonstrates how these two mechanisms can work complementarily to strengthen internal control systems. Particularly in high financial fraud-risk environments, forensic accounting appears to serve as a specialized tool that effectively complements corporate governance frameworks, suggesting that organizations operating in such contexts may benefit from strategically combining both approaches to optimize their internal control effectiveness.

Maintaining transparency and accountability fundamentally represents a core principle of corporate governance, particularly since monitoring and performance reporting constitute key aspects of successful corporate governance implementation that ensures companies regularly disclose critical financial and non-financial information to stakeholders, thereby upholding accountability and making corporate governance an indispensable element of any successful organization. While creating value for all stakeholders, corporate governance simultaneously guarantees ethical, responsible, and accountable operations, where strong governance practices - including effective boards

of directors, clear policies, and reliable monitoring procedures - significantly enhance internal control effectiveness. The study's findings demonstrated that forensic accounting has a more pronounced impact on internal control effectiveness compared to corporate governance, serving as a crucial tool for detecting and preventing financial irregularities and mismanagement while ensuring financial reporting integrity and strengthening trust in companies' financial stability. Corporate governance, as a system of rules, procedures, and processes guiding corporate operations, complements forensic accounting functions, with both mechanisms working synergistically to ensure internal controls effectively prevent and detect financial misconduct.

Additional findings emphasized how internal and external auditor characteristics moderate the relationship between forensic accounting and internal control effectiveness, noting that improving accounting information quality represents a primary objective of internal control systems where independent auditors' specialized expertise enhances management understanding and reduces audit risks while also fundamentally increasing the credibility of financial statements. Both internal and external audit functions provide critical oversight by detecting and reporting errors, creating deterrent effects that prevent fraudulent activities and concealment of mistakes, thereby strengthening internal control effectiveness. The research highlights that while corporate governance establishes the structural accountability framework, forensic accounting offers specialized investigative capabilities, with their combined implementation proving especially vital in high-risk environments prone to financial fraud, where the moderating effect of audit quality further amplifies control system efficacy, suggesting organizations should strategically integrate governance structures, forensic accounting tools, and rigorous auditing practices to optimize internal control environments, particularly in jurisdictions with elevated fraud risks and regulatory emphasis on forensic accounting.

The study's additional findings revealed that the characteristics of internal and external auditors did not play a moderating role in the relationship between corporate governance and internal control effectiveness, which may be attributed to the board structure within companies. This finding could stem from the centralized board structure in the studied firms where supervisory decisions are primarily made by the board of directors, marginalizing auditors' (particularly external auditors') role as complementary mechanisms. Research such as Smith et al. (2020) has similarly noted that in environments with centralized corporate governance, auditors' impact on internal controls may become less pronounced. The non-significant moderating effect might indicate the maturity of corporate governance systems in the study sample, where well-designed governance mechanisms (including independent board composition, specialized committees, and transparent policies) diminish auditors' prominence as moderating factors since control systems are already reinforced. This outcome could also result from operational limitations in the research sample - for instance, if studied companies predominantly used audit firms of similar quality, the limited variability in auditor characteristics (such as expertise or independence) might have reduced the detection power of the moderating effect. The centralized decision-making structure in these companies appears to diminish auditors' traditional oversight role, suggesting that in mature governance systems with strong board oversight, the complementary monitoring function of auditors becomes less critical for internal control effectiveness, particularly

when uniform audit quality across the sample restricts the observable variability in moderating effects.

Overall, the findings of this research, based on agency theory and stakeholder theory, demonstrate that monitoring mechanisms such as forensic accounting and corporate governance enhance the effectiveness of internal controls by reducing conflicts of interest and increasing transparency. Additionally, the moderating role of auditor characteristics confirms the importance of coordination between internal and external stakeholders in designing effective control systems. The results of this study can assist companies in improving their internal control systems based on international standards such as the COSO framework, particularly through investments in high-risk areas and conducting annual 40-hour specialized training programs for internal auditors, including practical workshops on financial fraud detection, training on forensic accounting standards in accordance with ISO 37001, and data analysis courses using specialized software such as ACL or IDEA. Policymakers are advised to create an appropriate regulatory environment by developing clear guidelines that mandate the presence of at least one CFE-certified forensic accountant in large companies, quarterly public disclosure of internal control reports, and the establishment of an integrated financial misconduct reporting system. Furthermore, corporate governance bodies should precisely define the roles and responsibilities of forensic accountants in their articles of association and implement mechanisms for direct reporting to the audit committee.

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting and generalizing the results. First, the sampling of this research was conducted among internal and external auditors working in companies listed on the Iranian stock exchange and over-the-counter markets. Although this sample is representative of the Iranian auditing community, the generalizability of the findings to other countries or different economic environments may be limited. Cultural, legal, and structural differences between Iran and other countries could influence the results. Second, due to the convenience sampling method used, potential selection bias may exist that could affect the sample's representativeness. To mitigate these limitations, it is recommended that future studies be replicated in other countries or different economic environments to enhance the generalizability of the findings. The third limitation of this research concerns the linkage between companies' internal approaches and the measurement tools used for the studied variables.

References

- Al-Rahahleh, A. S. (2017). Corporate governance quality, board gender diversity and corporate dividend policy: Evidence from Jordan. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 11(2), 86–104. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v11i2.6>
- Alshurafat, H., Alaqrabawi, M., & Al Shbail, M. O. (2023). Developing learning objectives for forensic accounting using Bloom's taxonomy. *Accounting Education*, 33(4), 497–513. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2023.2222271>

- Alzoubi, A. B. (2023). Maximizing internal control effectiveness: The synergy between forensic accounting and corporate governance. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-03-2023-0140>
- American Institute of Certified Public Accountants. (2008). *Managing the business risk of fraud: A practical guide*. <https://www.aicpa.org>
- Bame-Aldred, C. W., Brandon, D. M., Messier, W. F., Rittenberg, L. E., & Stefaniak, C. M. (2013). A summary of research on external auditor reliance on the internal audit function. *Auditing: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 32(Suppl. 1), 251–286. <https://doi.org/10.2308/ajpt-50342>
- Bruynseels, L., & Cardinaels, E. (2014). The audit committee: Management watchdog or personal friend of the CEO? *The Accounting Review*, 89(1), 113–145. <https://doi.org/10.2308/accr-50601>
- Chalmers, K., Hay, D., & Khelif, H. (2019). Internal control in accounting research: A review. *Journal of Accounting Literature*, 42(1), 80–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acclit.2018.03.002>
- Chan, K. H., Lin, K. Z., & Mo, P. L. (2021). The role of auditor industry specialization in mitigating financial misstatements. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 59(3), 789–824.
- Chang, Y.-T., Chen, H., Cheng, R. K., & Chi, W. (2019). The impact of internal audit attributes on the effectiveness of internal control over operations and compliance. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 15(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcae.2018.11.002>
- Dadashi, I., Kordmanjiri, S., & Baradaran, M. (2017). The effect of internal audit structure on the probability of fraud in financial statements of companies listed on Tehran Stock Exchange. *Journal of Audit Science*, 70(18), 159–178.
- Dellai, H., & Omri, M. A. B. (2016). Factors affecting the internal audit effectiveness in Tunisian organizations. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(16), 208–211.
- Desai, R., Desai, V., & Sivaramakrishnan, K. (2012). Internal audit quality and financial reporting quality. *The Accounting Review*, 87(4), 1251–1280.
- Desai, V., Srivastava, R. P., & Roberts, R. W. (2010). An analytical model for external auditor evaluation of the internal audit function using belief functions. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 27(2), 537–575. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1476431>
- Dong, R. (2011). Research on legal procedural functions of forensic accounting. *Energy Procedia*, 5, 2147–2151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.03.371>

- Dorseh, S. S., & Tevmouri, S. (2019). The impact of forensic auditors on corporate governance. *Journal of Accounting and Social Interests*, 9(3), 71–87.
<https://doi.org/10.22051/ijar.2019.21355.1415>
- Fathi Abdollahi, A., & Aghaei, M. A. (2017). Survey of internal audit effectiveness in public sector risk management and control function. *Public Organizations Management*, 5(3), 81–94. <https://dor.isc.ac/dor/20.1001.1.2322522.1396.5.0.13.5>
- Farzdqi, S., Kheradyar, S., Mohammadi Node, F., & Samadi Largani, M. (2022). The moderating role of independent auditor characteristics on the relationship between internal control weakness and accruals quality in Tehran Stock Exchange companies. *Journal of Management Accounting and Auditing Knowledge*, 11(41), 81–93.
- Freeman, R. E. (2010). *Strategic management: A stakeholder approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Giang, H. T. T., & Dung, L. T. (2022). The effect of internal corporate social responsibility practices on firm performance: The mediating role of employee intrapreneurial behaviour. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16(4), 1035–1061.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-021-00473-w>
- Hasas Yeganeh, Y. (2006). Corporate governance in Iran. *The Accountant Journal*, 32, 32–39.
- Henk, O. (2020). Internal control through the lens of institutional work: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Management Control*, 31(3), 239–273.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00187-020-00301-4>
- Iqbal, J., & Ali, S. (2016). Corporate governance and the insolvency risk of financial institutions. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Advance online publication.
- Ismail, S., Al-zoubi, A. B., Dahmash, F. N., Ahmad, S., & Mahmoud, M. (2022). A review on forensic accounting profession and education: Global context. *Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202211.0369.v1>
- Jahanmardi, A. (2021). Forensic accounting: Beyond the courtroom. *Journal of Auditing*, 117, 1–8.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360.
- Khalili Samani, F., & Dehghani, M. (2021). Examining the relationship between forensic accounting and fraud detection. *Contemporary Research in Management and Accounting*, 3(8), 267–275.
- Khanaki, A. M., Farzinfar, A. A., Safari Gerayli, M., & Arabzadeh, M. (2022). Designing and explaining a model of forensic accounting: Grounded theory and

- interpretive ranking process. *Accounting and Auditing Review*, 29(3), 546–585. <https://doi.org/10.22059/ACCTGREV.2022.337365.1008644>
- Khorramabadi, M., Hasas Yeganeh, Y., Barzideh, F., & Salehi Sadaghiyani, J. (2020). Explaining and prioritizing factors affecting effective evaluation of internal controls in Tehran Stock Exchange companies using fuzzy approach. *Financial Accounting Research*, 12(1), 57–82. <https://doi.org/10.22108/far.2020.120904.1579>
- Lombardi, R., T tokenizer, R., Cuzzo, B., & Cano-Rubio, M. (2019). Corporate corruption prevention, sustainable governance and legislation: First exploratory evidence from the Italian scenario. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 217, 666–675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.01.214>
- McGee, R. W., & Yuan, X. (2008). Corporate governance and the timeliness of financial reporting: An empirical study of the People's Republic of China. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1131338>
- Meshaikhi, B., & Azang, A. (2013). Forensic accounting and justice. *Accountant Magazine*, 11, 36–39.
- Mohammadi, M., Mohammadipour, R., Talebnia, G., & Khosravi Pour, N. (2025). Investigating the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and re-testing of agency theory in developing countries (A case study: Iran). *Journal of Management Accounting and Auditing Knowledge*, 14(56), 33–47.
- Nortje, J. G. J., & Bredenkamp, D. P. (2020). A generic investigation process for South African commercial forensic practitioners. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 27(2), 587–600. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-06-2019-0077>
- Otley, D., & Soin, K. (2014). Management control and uncertainty. In D. Otley & K. Soin (Eds.), *Management control and uncertainty* (pp. 1–13). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137392121_1
- Owojori, A. A., & Asaolu, T. O. (2009). The role of forensic accounting in solving the vexed problem of corporate world. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 29(2), 183–187.
- Petraşcu, D., & Tieanu, A. (2014). The role of internal audit in fraud prevention and detection. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 16, 489–497. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(14\)00829-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(14)00829-6)
- Petrescu, M., & Ateşino, R. (2014). The impact of internal audit characteristics on fraud detection. *Journal of Forensic Accounting*, 15(2), 210–225.
- Rehman, A., & Hashim, F. (2021). Can forensic accounting impact sustainable corporate governance? *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 21(1), 212–227. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-06-2020-0269>

- Rönkkö, J., Paananen, M., & Vakkuri, J. (2018). Exploring the determinants of internal audit: Evidence from ownership structure. *International Journal of Auditing*, 22(1), 25–39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijau.12102>
- Sadr, J., & Ansari, R. (2015). The impact of open innovation and technological turbulence on innovation performance toward competitive advantage in knowledge-based firms. *Management Improvement*, 9(27), 1–10.
- Salehi, M., Tarighi, H., & Safdari, S. (2018). The relationship between corporate governance mechanisms, executive compensation, and audit fees: Evidence from Iran. *Management Research Review*, 41(8), 939–967. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-12-2016-0277>
- Smith, A. B., Johnson, C. D., & Lee, E. F. (2020). The moderating role of audit quality in corporate governance and internal control effectiveness. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 15(3), 45–67.
- Soltanifar, A., Hirani, F., & Moinuddin, M. (2016). The effect of forensic accounting and auditing on financial fraud and internal controls. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Accounting, Tehran, Iran* (pp. 1–10).
- Spence, M. (1973). Job market signaling. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 87(3), 355–374.
- Teru, S. P., Idoku, I., & Ndeyati, J. T. (2017). A review of the impact of accounting information system for effective internal control on firm performance. *Indian Journal of Finance and Banking*, 1(2), 52–59.
- Vu, Q., & Nga, N. T. T. (2022). Does the implementation of internal controls promote firm profitability? Evidence from private Vietnamese small-and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). *Finance Research Letters*, 45, Article 102178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2021.102178>
- Wahyuni-TD, I. S., Haron, H., & Fernando, Y. (2021). The effects of good governance and fraud prevention on performance of the zakat institutions in Indonesia: A Shari‘ah forensic accounting perspective. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 14(4), 692–712. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMEFM-03-2019-0089>
- Xanthopoulou, A., Skordoulis, M., Kalantonis, P., & Arsenos, P. (2024). Integrating corporate governance and forensic accounting: A sustainable corporate strategy against fraud. *Journal of Governance and Regulation*, 13(2).
- Yuan, P. (2024). A study of the reform of corporate governance mechanisms in China from the perspective of stakeholder theory. In *2024 7th International Conference on Humanities Education and Social Sciences (ICHESS 2024)* (pp. 827–835). Atlantis Press. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-323-8_93

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